

THEORETICAL ESTIMATION AND EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENT OF HYBRID EFFECT OF HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work deals with the problem of theoretical estimation of hybrid effect of sandwich, interply and intraply hybrid composites, consisting of carbon and glass fibres, in tensile experiment. A microstructure parameter -- dispersion coefficient is defined as the description of the dispersion of different kinds of fibres in hybrid composites and it can be used for quantitative comparison of the dispersion of fibres in different hybrid composites. The paper reveals the quantitative relationship between hybrid ratio and fibre dispersion. An experimental formula is established to estimate hybrid effect. The estimated values are in good agreement with experimental ones. The established formula would have certain guiding significance for materials design of hybrid composite structural components.

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composite materials have nowadays become an important developing tendency of composites due to their wide designing freedom, broad performance adaptability and apparent economic benefit. And they have been widely used in the fields of automobile industry, aero-space industry, sports articles and architecture etc.

One of the important problems that must be taken into account in the course of designing and using hybrid composites is the so-called hybrid effect. As early as the beginning of 1970's, Hayashi et al¹ began a research on hybrid effect and since then, many scholars have paid great attention to it. In Kretsis' recently issued review,² he summarized the achievements in this aspect in the last ten years, and he revealed the relationship between hybrid effect and fibre dispersion, as well as the relative content of LE (low elongation) fiber. He pointed out that the hybrid effect increased with the decreasing of the content of LE fibre and the increasing of dispersion of such fibre. In this work, we studied systematically the law of effect of hybrid ratio and fibre dispersion on hybrid effect and established an experienced formula estimating hybrid effect, including the above two factors and the effect of laminate thickness. The estimated values of hybrid effect using the formula are in good agreement with experimental ones. The revelation and application of hybrid effect would be of certain guiding significance for materials design of hybrid composite structural components.

EXPERIMENT

1. Raw materials

The types and properties of raw materials used in the experiment are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 The properties of reinforcement and matrix

Performance	Reinforcement		Matrix
	Carbon fibre	Glass fibre	
Density	1.77* a)	2.54	Epoxy resin, 648#/BF ₃ ·MEA
Tensile modulus (GPa)	230	85.4	
Tensile strength (GPa)	2.95*	2.76*	
Failure elongation (%)	1.2	3.3	

a)* stands for actually measured values.

2. Specimen preparation of hybrid composites

The prepregs of carbon and glass fibres with epoxy resin 648#/BF₃·MEA system (weight ratio of resin to curing agent is equal to 100:3) are laid up according to hybrid structure forms required. The specimens are cured in terms of normal autoclave technology.

3. Performance testing

Tensile experiment based on GB 3354-82.*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Dispersion coefficient of hybrid composites

In order to describe hybrid composites completely, it is required to introduce two important parameters: hybrid ratio and fibre dispersion.³ Hybrid ratio can be expressed by V_{Lf} (relative volume fraction of LE fibre in hybrid composites). However, for a long time, it is failed to find a rational way to express fibre dispersion. Usually, we can only qualitatively divide hybrid composites into interply, intraply and sandwich etc.. Somebody also tried to express it in terms of interface number. Manders and Bader⁴ suggested to use Dispersion to describe fibre dispersion quantitatively. It is illustrated in Fig.1 and the definition of Dispersion is presented as follows:

$$\text{Dispersion} = \frac{1}{t_r} \quad (1)$$

where: t_r is the thickness of minimum repeat unit of hybrid composite. However, through observation and analysis, we find out that, when using the equation (1) to express fibre dispersion, the minimum repeat unit number contained in the whole specimen, as well as the effect of factors of lay-up and laminate thickness and so on are not taken into account. But the influence of size effect on hybrid effect is actually quite great⁵. It has also been verified in our experiment.

* GB is National Standard of China.

Fig.1 The illustration of fibre dispersion
 t_r : the thickness of minimum repeat unit

Based on the concept of the minimum repeat unit, we introduce a dispersion coefficient ϕ to express fibre dispersion. It is presented as follows:

$$\phi = \frac{H_{hy}/M_{hy}}{\frac{H_g \cdot N_g}{M_g} + \frac{H_c \cdot N_c}{M_c}} \quad (2)$$

where: H_{hy} is hybrid laminate thickness; M_{hy} is total lay-up number of hybrid laminate; H_g , H_c are the thickness of single glass and single carbon fibre composite laminates respectively; N_g , N_c are the glass and carbon fibre lay-up numbers respectively contained in the minimum repeat unit in hybrid composites; M_g , M_c are the lay-up numbers of single glass and single carbon fibre composite laminates respectively.

The computed values for ϕ are listed in Table.2. From the data in Table. 2, it can be found that the value for ϕ can quantitatively reflect fibre dispersion in hybrid composites. And we can also find in the next section that the value for ϕ has close relationship with hybrid effect coefficient R_h . It is the main purpose that we introduce such a concept in this paper.

2. Estimation of hybrid effect

In 1972, Hayashi¹ firstly found out that the values of failure strain and strength of LE fibre in hybrid composites were higher than those of composites consisting of LE fibre, and this phenomenon was called as "hybrid effect". Furthermore, he proposed to use a hybrid effect coefficient R_h to describe the hybrid effect quantitatively:

$$R_h = \frac{E_h - E_c}{E_c} \quad (3)$$

where: E_h , E_c are the primary failure elongation of hybrid composites and carbon fibre composites respectively.

Table.2 The value for ϕ of interply and sandwich hybrid specimens*

Types	No. of Specimen	Form of lay-up	dispersion coefficient ϕ	hybrid interfacial number
Sandwich	6	(GG) _s	0.0895	2
	16	(C ₂ G ₄) _s	0.0965	2
	12	(C ₃ G ₃) _s	0.108	2
Interply	8	(CG) _{3s}	0.508	10
	14	(GG ₂ CG) _s	0.342	8
	18	(C ₂ GCGC) _s	0.485	8

* C, G stand for carbon and glass plies respectively.

From Fig.2, it can be seen that the value for R_h has a relation to ϕ and V_{Lf} . The value for R_h decreases with the increasing of the values for ϕ . It tells us that R_h is the function of V_{Lf} and ϕ . By analysing and comparing, we can obtained and experienced formula as follows:

$$R_h = K^2 \cdot \phi \cdot (1 - V_{Lf}) \quad (4)$$

where: K is hybrid structure parameter, for interply: K=1, for sandwich: K=2.

The estimated and experimental results are listed in Table.3. It can be seen that they are quite close. Some differences of R_h between the estimated and experimental values is attributed to the neglecting of heat effect⁴. However, the estimated value for specimen No.14 is lower obviously. By analysing from the stacking sequence, we know that it result from the fact that HE (high elongation) fibre is located at outmost ply, which stops the cracks of internal carbon plies from propagating. If one wants to get higher value for R_h , we suggest to use the structure with HE fibre ply at the outmost.

Fig.2. The relationship between hybrid effect coefficient R_h and relative content of LE fibre.

Table.3 The comparison of actually measured values of R_h with estimated R_h of hybrid composites

Types	No. of specimen	Form of ply-up	$V_{L1}, \%$	Actually measures value, R_h	Estimated value, R_h
Single	1	$(G_6)_s$	0		
	3	$(C_8)_s$	100		
Sandwich	6	$(CG_5)_s$	15.43	0.301	0.303
	16	$(C_2G_4)_s$	28.57	0.205	0.251
	12	$(C_3G_3)_s$	46.10	0.205	0.234
Interply	14	$(GCG_2CG)_s$	29.73	0.395	0.241
	8	$(CG)_3s$	46.07	0.265	0.270
	18	$(C_2GCGC)_s$	63.61	0.241	0.171
	20	$(CK)_3s$	48.18	0.156	0.144
Intraply	22	C/G two by two	73.49	0.168	

3. Conclusions

A. Through theoretical analysis and experimental study, we suggested to add a new parameter, dispersion coefficient, to describe hybrid composite. Experimental results prove that dispersion coefficient is an important structural parameter for hybrid composites.

B. Hybrid effect is associated with relative fibre content and dispersion coefficient. In this paper, we established an experienced formula to estimate hybrid effect. The formula can estimate the value for R_h of sandwich and interply hybrid. It provides theoretical and experimental basis for materials design of hybrid composite structural components and for establishing constitutive equation of analysing material structure and strength.

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